

CO₂-SPICER - CO₂ Storage Pilot In a CarbonatE Reservoir

R2.6 Maps of initial and current contacts of fluids in the reservoir

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April 2022

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1 INTRODUCTION

After detailed interpretation of 3D seismic, construction of surfaces of key horizons and construction of the static reservoir model and petrophysical properties distribution in Schlumberger Petrel software, the maps of original and recent fluid contacts were constructed. The top of reservoir formation within the final model grid served as the main input for the map construction. The original depths of the gas - oil contact (GOC) and oil - water contact (OWC) were derived from the well log interpretation reports by Hrubý (2004, 2011). The recent contact levels were derived from interpretation of recent neutron logs from ZA3 well within the Zar-3 (Žarošice) oil and gas field.

2 WELL LOGS EVALUATION - CONTACTS

The fluid contacts were evaluated in suitable wells. The evaluation was based on well logging measurements results and results of hydrocarbon saturation interpretation (Hrubý 2004). Following contacts were set apart: GOC – gas, oil contact, OOWC – the oil, water contact including the water transmission zone, SOWC – the oil, water contact without water transmission zone and possibly influenced by the oil or water production (Tab. 2-1). The final initial contact at level 1600.8 m (SSTVD – sub-sea level true vertical depth) was used for dynamic simulations. The recent contact set was derived from the neutron logging in well ZA3 (Fig. 2-1).

Tab. 2-1: Gas, oil and oil, water contacts were calculated using the well log interpretation results.

Well	GOC		SOWC		OOWC	
	MD [m]	SSTVD [m]	MD [m]	SSTVD [m]	MD [m]	SSTVD [m]
ZA3	1711,1	1487,3	1824,9	1600,8	1848,1	1623,9
ZA4A	1746,3	1487,5	1848,6	1589,8	1889,1	1630,3
ZA6A	1853,5	1487,4	1967,3	1599,9	1995,5	1627,8
ZA7			1896,0	1593,3		
field		1487,4		1598,0		1627,3

Fig. 2-1: Gas, oil and oil, water contacts derived from neutron logging in ZA3 well.

3 CONTACT MAPS CONSTRUCTION

The maps were constructed for the top of main reservoir zones Vranovice Formation and Nikolčice Formation. The maps were constructed for the original gas, oil, water contacts in Vranovice Formation (Fig. 3-1), Nikolčice Formation (Fig. 3-2) and recent gas, oil, water contacts in Vranovice Formation (Fig. 3-3) and Nikolčice Formation (Fig. 3-4). The initial contacts were also imported into the dynamic reservoir model grid (Figs. 3-5 and 3-6).

Fig. 3-1: Zar-3 oil and gas field. Depth map of Vranovice Fm. top with initial gas, oil and water contacts highlighted.

Fig. 3-2: Zar-3 oil and gas field. Depth map of Vranovice Fm. top with recent (2022) gas, oil and water contacts highlighted.

Fig. 3-3: Zar-3 oil and gas field. Depth map of Nikolčice Fm. top with initial gas, oil and water contacts highlighted.

Fig. 3-4: Zar-3 oil and gas field. Depth map of Nikolčice Fm. top with recent gas, oil and water contacts highlighted.

Fig. 3-5: Zar-3 oil and gas field. 3D view of cross section through reservoir zones in dynamic model with gas, oil and water zones highlighted (red colour – gas, green colour – oil, blue colour – water).

Fig. 3-6: Zar-3 oil and gas field. 3D view on top of reservoir zones in dynamic model with gas, oil and water zones highlighted (red colour – gas, green colour – oil, blue colour – water).

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This report is a result of the CO₂-SPICER project
(CO₂ Storage Pilot In a CarbonatE Reservoir) - project No: TO01000112.

The CO₂-SPICER project benefits from a €2.32 mil grant
from Norway and Technology Agency of the Czech Republic.

More information about the project can be found at
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